

Microsatellite Instability of Circadian Clock Genes in Oral Squamous Cell Carcinoma and Efficacy of Anti-Tumour DrugsSeema Gupta¹, Rajeev Gupta², Biswajit Maity³^{1,2}Professor, Department of Radiation Oncology, King George's Medical University, Lucknow, India³Associate Professor, Department of Biochemistry & Head, Research & Development, Hind Institute of Medical Sciences, Ataria, Sitapur, UP, India

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Abstract:

Background: Circadian system coordinated and regulated multiple cellular procedures which implicating in cancer development such as metabolism, cell cycle and DNA damage response. Many studies suggested that clock genes contribute to the regulation of not only circadian rhythm, but also the regulation of apoptosis induced by anti-tumour drugs. In this study 13 Microsatellite markers of Circadian-Clock Genes were examined in 150 OSCC patients treated with cisplatin + 5FU (Arm-I) and Cisplatin + capecitabin (Arm-II) to establish genetic marker for early detection as well as the marker responsible for drugs sensitivity and resistance for accurate clinical practice.

Results: Overall incidence of LOH/MSI was 49%±18.84 with the frequency of LOH and MSI of individual markers ranged from 12-71%. LOH was relatively more frequently detected at five loci, namely Bmal-1 (42%), Per-1 (46%), Per-2(49%), rorβ (58%), c-fos (49%), whereas the MIS of above five markers were 53%, 65%, 69%, 63% and 71% respectively. Low incidence of MSI was observed in Clock-5 (16%), Rora (12%) and E4BP4 (17%).

Conclusion: The results of this study suggested that the microsatellites of Clock genes particularly Bmal-1, per-2, Rorβ and C-fos may be used as a marker to determine clinical staging, to evaluate the metastatic risk of OSCC, and as a novel target for the prevention and treatment of OSCC.

Keywords: Circadian Clock Gene-Microsatellites, Oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC), Clock Genes RNA Expression. Cisplatin + 5Fu & Cisplatin + Capecitabin.

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Introduction

Head and neck cancer is the sixth most common cancer diagnosed globally. Oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC) is the most common head and neck cancer. There are more than 350 000 new cases of OSCC every year in the world, and approximately 170 000 people die from OSCC annually [1-3]. OSCC has a poor prognosis. Currently, the main methods of treatment for OSCC are surgical resection, adjuvant radiotherapy and chemotherapy. Although surgical techniques, radiotherapy and chemotherapy have made great progress over the past 30 years, the 5-year survival rate of OSCC patients has remained at approximately 50% and has not increased significantly.[4,5]

Clock genes create a complicated molecular time-keeping system consisting of multiple positive and negative feedback loops at transcriptional and translational levels. This circadian system coordinates and regulates multiple cellular procedures implicated in cancer development such

as metabolism, cell cycle and DNA damage response[6].To date, there are at least nine demonstrated major circadian-clock genes, ie, period1 (Per1), period2 (Per2), period3 (Per3), circadian locomotor output cycles kaput (Clock), cryptochrome1 (Cry1), cryptochrome2 (Cry2), brain and muscle Arnt-like protein 1 (Bmal 1), casein kinase 1ε (CK1ε), and timeless (Tim).[7] It has been reported recently that the occurrence, development, prognosis, and treatment of various cancer like prostate, head and neck squamous cell carcinoma, Colorectal etc are closely related to the abnormal expression of certain circadian-clock genes [8,9]

A lower expression level of PER1, PER2, and PER3 has also been documented in diseased tissue compared to normal adjacent tissue in breast cancer, prostate cancer, colorectal cancer, pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma, gastric cancer, kidney cancer and non-small-cell lung cancer [10,11]. Recent data advocated that the molecules

such as CLOCK1, BMAL1 and PER and CRY proteins have various effects on c-Myc/p21 and Wnt/ β -catenin pathways and influenced multiple steps of DNA damage which was responded for playing a critical role in the preservation of genomic integrity in normal and cancer cells [12]. It has been found that the circadian rhythmicity of critical mediators of the circadian system, namely PER1, PER2, REV-ERBA was significantly decreased in Colorectal cancer tissues while the rhythmicity of BMAL1, another circadian rhythm component was completely abolished not only in the CRC tissues but in the surrounding healthy colon tissue as well in tumor bearing animals[13].

A recent study showed that CLOCK1 gene was somatically mutated in 53% of CRC characterized by MSI. According to this study, CLOCK1 promoted growth arrest, DNA repair and apoptosis upon genotoxic stress caused by UV radiation suggesting that this molecule may represent an important “caretaker” promoting cell cycle arrest upon DNA damage [14].

The PER1 circadian-clock gene plays an important role in the regulation of many normal physiological rhythms *in vivo*. It has been revealed recently that abnormal expression of PER1 correlated closely with the occurrence and development of many cancers. It has been documented that the expression of PER1 mRNA and protein in Oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC) was significantly reduced compared with that in adjacent noncancerous tissue subsequently expression of PER1 protein in oral phase III–IV SCC specimens was significantly lower than that in phase I–II specimens, and stage T1–T2 patients expressed significantly higher levels of PER1 protein than T3–T4 patients and also the expression of PER1 in patients without lymph node metastasis was significantly higher than that in those with lymph node metastasis. PER1 protein expression showed no significant correlation with patient gender and age, or with degree of tumor cell differentiation [15,16].

Clock and brain-muscle-arnt-like-protein 1 (Bmal1) are dominant positive regulators of circadian rhythm. PER negatively regulates the transactivation of Clock/Bmal1.24 Clock/ Bmal1 mutants or knockout mice affected the sensitivity to the anti-tumour drug cyclophosphamide. These findings suggested that clock genes contribute to the regulation of not only circadian rhythm, but also the regulation of apoptosis induced by anti-tumour drugs [16].

Cis-Diamminedichloroplatinum (II) (cisplatin: CDDP) is one of the most important anti-tumour drugs, and CDDP treatment induces DNA-damage and leads to apoptosis in various solid tumours. CDDP treatment also affects transcription, translation, DNA repair and the cell cycle, although

some tumours are resistant to CDDP treatment. Several mechanisms are thought to be involved in the acquisition of resistance to CDDP. Tumours that are resistant to CDDP often shown decreased drug accumulation and increased DNA-repair activity and transcription factor activity [17]. It has been also reported that the CDDP treatment of CA9-22 cells increased the amount of PER1, but not PER3, in the nucleus. The observed differences between PER1 and PER3 with regard to their roles in the regulation of apoptosis may be related to differences in their subcellular localisation [18]. Therapeutics Response Portal and Genomics of Drug Sensitivity in Cancer projects showed that clock genes could be drug targets, which suggested that the potential of combining cancer chronotherapy and immunotherapy for better outcomes of mCRC patients subsequently the study revealed that the expressions of CLOCK, CRY1 and NPAS2 were significantly changed in the TGF- β dominant subtype, that provides preliminary evidence for the potential of using cancer chronotherapy for the regimens of mCRC immunotherapy[19]. It has also been demonstrated that the abnormal circadian clock contributes to T cell exhaustion and global upregulation of immune inhibitory molecules such as PD-L1 and CTLA-4 which linked with immune evasion and may serve as a potential hallmark of cancer [20]. A study results identified CRY2, NR1D1, and PER2 as potential prognostic biomarkers for COAD patients and correlated their expression with immune cell infiltration and also advocated that the Inc-RNA KCNQ1OT1/hsa-miRNA-32-5p/PER2/CRY2 regulatory axis which was detected in COAD might play a vital role in the occurrence and progression of COAD [21].

A study suggested that, in OSCC specimens and cell lines, Bmal1 expression was decreased, and its rhythmic pattern was changed. Furthermore, Bmal1 overexpression resulted in an increase in the apoptotic cell population after exposure of cells to paclitaxel and enhanced paclitaxel sensitivity *in vivo*. Other research showed that paclitaxel efficacy was influenced by the Bmal1 expression level in OSCC. Consequently, Bmal1 acts as a tumor suppressor gene that elevated the sensitivity of cancer cells to paclitaxel [22].

Allelic imbalance in tumor suppressor genes is the key event in OSCC which is associated with loss of heterozygosity mostly on chromosome 17q25, 9p21 etc [23] It was also reported that the GG genotypes of MSH2 rs3732183 and MLH1 rs1800734 are associated with relatively high survival in OSCC patients treated using adjuvant CCRT and these polymorphisms may serve as prognosis predictors in OSCC patients [24] A few Microsatellite markers at chromosome regions 2p21 (D2S2259, 65.00%), 4q12 (D4S1592,

53.57%), 5p13.2 (D5S426, 52.63%), 5p15.1 (D5S416, 65.22%), 5q35.1 (D5S400, 58.82%), 7q21.13 (D7S630, 56.00%) and 19q13.43 (D19S210, 55.17%) were pinpointed as frequent LOH regions which also detected early changes in OSCC [25-27].

To the best of our knowledge no documents were available on Microsatellite Instability, Loss of Heterozygosity of circadian-clock genes in OSCC.

Hence, this Circadian-Clock Genes could be targeted as a marker for OSCC as well as therapeutic validation to meet the clinical challenges.

The aim of this study was to examine Microsatellite markers of Circadian-Clock Genes in OSCC patients treated with cisplatin and capecitabine to establish genetic marker for early detection as well as the marker responsible for drugs sensitivity and resistance for accurate clinical practice.

Materials and Methods

Patients and samples

In this study, a total of 150 primary tumor tissues, and corresponding blood samples from patients attending the King Georges Medical University, Lucknow from 2016 to 2019, were collected. The tissue samples were obtained, either at the time of investigative biopsy or during the time of the surgical resection of the lesions. Written informed consent in accordance with Institutional Review Board guidelines was taken from all patients. One portion of the biopsy was utilized for routine histopathological examination and the rest was frozen immediately and stored in liquid nitrogen. Peripheral blood lymphocytes from the patients, used to assess the microsatellites as well as mRNA expression of Circadian Clock Genes, were stored at -80C until DNA/ RNA extraction.

Histopathological diagnosis was also performed according to standard criteria.

Figure 1: Immunohistochemistry for p40 shown diffuse nuclear positivity in tumor cells (200xmagnification)

Clinicopathological staging was determined as per UICC TNM staging system version 6. Patients then received standard treatment based on tumor stage and individual clinical status.

RNA isolation:

Total RNA was isolated using the RNeasy extraction kit (Qiagen), including DNase digestion, according to manufacturer's instructions. Cells/ tissues were lysed with 350 μ l RLT buffer (with 1% beta mercaptoethanol) and lysate was homogenized. Total RNA concentration was determined by OD260 using an Ultraspec 3000 UV spectrophotometer and stored at 280uC.

cDNA synthesis and quantitative real-time PCR: 1 mg of total RNA was reverse transcribed to cDNA with 2 U/ml RevertAid M-MuLV reverse transcriptase and 500 mM random 15-mer primers (Fermentas). For quantitative SYBR-green based real-time PCR, used 20 ng of cDNA and the commercial primers from QuantiTect primer assays for Gapdh, Bmal1, Per1, Per2, Rora, Cry1, Cry2 and Clock etc (Qiagen). For each primer, a non-template control (NTC) was always included.

The reaction was performed in an ABI Prism 7000 SDS thermocycler (Applied Biosystems). The obtained data were analysed using the ABI Prism 7000 System SDS software (Applied Biosystems).

Each sample was measured in triplicates. The expression levels were normalized to those of Gapdh (DCT) and calibrated to the value at time 0 of the control cell line (DDCT). The relative quantification was performed using the 2^{-ΔΔCT} method [34].

Preparation of DNA and PCR

DNA was extracted from blood and tumor tissue using a proteinase K digestion and phenol–chloroform method (27). Thirteen microsatellite markers - Clock-5, Bmal1-6, Per1-11, Per2-1, Per3-4, Cry1-10, Cry2- 2, Rev-erbα, Rora, Rorβ, E4BP4, Dbp and C-fos were used in this study. Genetic map location, physical order and primer sequence of selected microsatellite markers, were obtained from the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI's UniSTS site, www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genome/sts/) (Table-1). The microsatellite primers were purchased from Bangalore Genie.

PCR reaction: - The microsatellite PCR was performed in 25 μl reaction volume containing 50 ng genomic DNA, 15 pmole each primer, 1.5 μl dNTPs (25 mM), 3.3 μl 10X assay buffer with MgCl₂ (15 mM), 0.6 μl Taq polymerase (3U/μl) (Bangalore Genie). DNA was amplified by PTC 200 MJ Research Thermocycler programme to provide first denaturation at 94°C for 5 min. followed by 35 cycles of 1 min. at 94°C, 1 min. at 57°C and 2 at 72°C and final extension at 72°C for 7 min. The PCR products were observed in 3% agarose gels (wide range A 2790 of Sigma).

Sample preparation and DNA fragment analysis

The gels were scanned and the raw data were analysed using the Fragment Manager software (Pharmacia Biotech). Preparation of the size marker, assessment of microsatellite instability (MSI) and LOH were performed as reported previously [16].

Allelic status (LOH) was assessed by comparing constitutionally heterozygous (informative) alleles with their corresponding tumour alleles. Microsatellite loci were regarded as having LOH if either the entire upper or lower tumour allele of informative cases were visually absent or exhibited a 50% or greater diminishment of the allele than the corresponding normal allele in DNA isolated from the lymphocytes of patients. Alterations were described as microsatellite instability (MSI) when any additional band which was not seen in normal DNA was seen in tumour DNA. Samples showing allelic loss were subjected to repeat analysis after a second independent amplification. The mathematic model of LOH determination used is the following: height of normal allele two + height of normal allele one/ height of tumour allele two + height of tumour allele one.

Mode of treatment

Treatment strategy for each patient was given on the basis of stages. Treatment modality was combination therapy (n = 150) [Arm-I = Cisplatin + 5 FU (n=72); Arm-II = cisplatin + capecitabine (n=78)

Results

A total of 150 patients with OSCC which included 132 (88%) men and 18 (12%) women with mean age at diagnosis of 55.3 years (range 38–73 for women, years) which was slightly lower in women than in men (men 49; range 42–82) but the difference was not significant. The tongue was the most frequent localization affected in 59 [Male-54, Female-5 (39.33%)], The buccal mucosa was affected in 47 [male-37, female-10 including one EP (31.33%)], Hard Palate was affected in 7 (4.66%), The lip was affected in 19 (12.66%). The Floor of mouth was most frequently affected in men 7 (4.66%), whereas in women 1 (0.66%). The solid type was more frequent in men (72%) than in females (59%), whereas the peripheral type was more frequent in females (28%) than in men (19%), these differences were also significant. Tumor status and death was found significant in this study (P≤0.05). The only unicystic case was observed in a male patient. Primary tumor size was measured to be on average 2.1 cm. Median size was 1.75 cm, with a range between 0.6 and 5.0 cm. The unicystic case displayed the largest size with a 2.5 cm diameter followed by solid and peripheral cases with a mean size of 2.1 and 2.0 cm, respectively. The mean follow-up was 3 months with a range of 1-2 months. All of the patients were alive at the date of the last documented follow up. Sixteen patients underwent radical surgery (67%) while the remaining ones underwent a conservative surgery (33%). No relationship was observed between the type of surgery and other variables, such as gender, histotype, localization and recurrence. Sixty five (43.3%) patients recurred during the period of follow-up, including 58 men (43.93%) and 7 (38.88%) women, (EP-1).

Table-1 and Figure-2 shown the results of microsatellites analysis and the distribution of LOH and MSI in 150 cases of OSCC. Overall incidence of LOH/MSI was 49%±18.84 with the frequency of LOH and MSI of individual markers ranged from 12-71%. LOH was relatively more frequently detected at five loci, namely Bmal-1 (42%), Per-1 (46%), Per-2(49%), rorβ (58%), c-fos (49%), whereas the MIS of above five markers were 53%, 65%, 69%, 63% and 71% respectively. Low incidence of MSI was observed in Clock-5 (16%), Rora (12%) and E4BP4 (17%). The incidence of LOH were highest in the tumors of tongue, buccal Mucosa and lip with multiple genetic loci range from 3 to 8. Remaining two tumors with LOH at double loci. MSI were detected in all tumors of tongue, buccal Mucosa and lip with at list 5 loci.

Furthermore, all tumors of tongue, buccal Mucosa and lip with LOH and MSI were from male patients whereas, 4% was observed in female. Presence of LOH was having no association with the age,

tumour size but tumour stage was significantly associated with LOH/MSI of the patients ($P \leq 0.05$). Mixed habit was also associated with LOH.

Table 1: Microsatellite Markers of Circadian-Clock Genes

Primers	Alleles, Size(bp) Frequencies	H _{obs} , H _{exp} LOH	MIS%
Clock-5	5, 307/0.65, 303/0.18, 304/0.09, 306/0.07, 302/0.01	0.63, 0.58, 24%	16%
	5'-TCG CCT CCA AGA ATG TAA GT - 3'		
	5 -TCT GCA TTT TAA CTA TGG CTC - 3'		
Bmal1-6	7,230/0.44, 232/0.42, 228/0.08, 224/0.03, 229/0.01, 226/0.01, 225/0.003	0.52, 0.57, 42%	53%
	5-CCA AGA AAG TAT GGA CAC AGA CAA A-3'		
	5-GCA TTC TTG ATC CTT CCT TGG T-3'		
Per1-11	4,168/0.14, 170/0.043, 174/0.13, 176/0.089	0.07 , 0.09, 46%	65%
	5-AAA CCT CTG GCT GTT CCT ACC A-3'		
	5-AAT GTT GCA GCT CTC CAA ATA CC-3'		
Per2-1	6,170/0.34, 168/0.098, 174/0.32, 180/0.075, 178/0.043, 169/0.023	0.72, 0.65, 49%	69%
	5'- TCA CAG GAT GCC TGC CTT TA3'		
	5'-AGT GCA TTT CTA TGG CTC-3'		
Per3-4	5, 146bp/0.065, 144/0.021, 138/0, 014, 140/0.043, 139/0.009	0.32, 0.97, 24%	19%
	5'-AGT TTC TTG ATC CTT CCT TGG T-3'		
	5'-TCA CAG GAT GCC TGC CTT TA		
Cry1-10	5, 200/0.65, 203/0.18, 197/0.09, 206/0.07, 194/0.01	0.69 , 0.64, 39%	27%
	5-AGT TCC CCT CCC CTT TCT CTT-3'		
	5-GGG TTC CCT TCC ATT TTG TCA-3'		

Cry2- 2	5,178/0.39, 181/0.21, 184/0.19, 175/0.19, 172/0.02	0.19, 0.23, 41%	37%
	5'CGA GAA AGT ATG GAC ACA GAC AAA-3'		
	5'-GCA AGA AAG TAT GGA CAC TGA CAA T-3'		
Rev-erba	7,162/0.44, 164/0.42, 163a/0.08, 166/0.03, 165a/0.01, 158/0.01, 160/0.003	0.24, 0.22, 42%	38%
	5' -ATG CTC GCC ATC CAC AAG A-3'		
	5' -GCG GAA TCG AAT GGG AGA AT-3'		
Rora	5, 383/0.09, 382/0.97, 380/0.93, 392/0.03, 376/0.091	0.16, 0.20, 23%	12%
	5' -AAGGTTGTCCACATACTTC-3'		
	5' -GTTTTTCAGACACCGTTTGT-3'		
Rorβ	5,278/0.19, 281/0.21, 284/0.17, 275/0.12, 272/0.02	0.39, 0.42, 58%	63%
	5'- AAA CAG GAT GCC TGC CTT TA - 3'		
	5' - GGA CTT TCC ACC TAT GGG AC - 3'		
E4BP4	2	0.32, 0.31, 12%	17%
	5' - AGC AGA TAA GAC AGT ATT ACT AGT T - 3'		
	5' - ACT CAC TCT AGT GAT AAA TCG GG - 3'		
Dbp	5, 146/0.065, 144/0.021, 138/0.014, 140/0.043, 139/0.009	0.27, 0.29, 33%	42%
	5' - GGA AGA ATC AAA TAG ACA AT - 3'		
	5' - GCT GGC CAT ATA TAT ATT TAA ACC - 3		
C-fos	7, 548/0.85, 546/0.05, 556/0.02, 540/0.02, 534/0.02, 550/0.01, 538/0.01	0.59, 0.65, 49%	71%
	5' -TGTGCCAGGGTGGTGACTT-3'		
	5' -TCAAATTTCTCTCCGTAGATGGACTT-3'		

Gpdh	144	c	c
	5' -CATCCCAGAGCTGAAC-3'		
	5' -TCAGATGCCTGCTTCAC-3'		

Figure 2: Six Microsatellite Markers amplified in OSCC Patients DNA

Table 2: OSCC Patients Showing Drugs response/Chemo Response against Circadian Clock Gene Microsatellite Loci.

SI No	Locus	Cisplatin + 5 Fu [Arm-I]			Cisplatin + Capecitabine (Arm-II)		
		CR	PR	NR	CR	PR	NR
1	PERIOD (PER-1)	1	1	0	0	1	0
2	PER3	0	1	0	0	0	0
3	BMAL1	1	0	1	0	1	0
4	CLOCK	1	0	0	1	0	1
5	CRY1	1	1	0	0	1	1
6	CRY2	9	7	1	6	9	2
7	PER2	24	6	0	23	11	3
8	Rev-Erb α	3	1	0	2	3	1
9	GAPDH-Control						
10	E4BP4	0	1	0	0	1	0
11	c-fos	22	5	1	19	3	3
12	Ror β	16	4	1	18	5	2
13	Ror α	5	1	0	3	2	0
14	Dbp	3	1	0	2	1	0

Figure 3: Post Treated Circadian genes expression in two treated groups with control

It has been found that, the mRNA expression of Clock & Clock-Controlled genes particularly Per3 [0.301(CT₀) – 0.401 (CT₁₆) –up regulated], Bmal1 [0.909(CT₀) -0.0207(CT₁₆)-down regulated] & E4BP4 [0.306(CT₀) - 0.509(CT₂₀)-up regulated] were remained significantly rhythmic ($p \leq 0.05$) as compared to control and two treated groups (Cis + Cap = Arm-II, and Cis + 5Fu= Arm-I). mRNA levels of c-fos(down regulated-0.603), Per1 (up regulated-0.794) & per2 (down regulated-0.976) in two treated groups, were also significantly expressed as compared to control. Microsatellite Instability particularly LOH loss of heterozygosity, Mismatch were found significantly higher (LOH-35-58%; MI-24-48%) of the above markers in Arm-II as compared to control.

Discussion:

It was reported that PER1 is a pro-apoptotic factor in human colon cancer and murine mammary tumour cells.[25]. On the contrary, it was also reported to be anti-apoptotic in human pancreatic cancer and hepatocellular carcinoma cells.[26]. PER1 regulates the expression of molecules involved in apoptosis or the cell cycle,[17,22] and its expression demonstrates a circadian rhythm in some tumour cells.[18,27] However, the effect of PER1 on apoptosis in the presence of anti-tumour drugs is unknown. The Present study demonstrated that PER-1,2 microsatellites were more strongly expressed in cancer cells than in adjacent non-tumour tissues. On the contrary, the expression of PER3 was less in tumour cells than in adjacent non-tumour cells. These results suggest that PER1 and PER3 are differentially regulated and play opposite roles in development of tumour tissues. A study advocated that the expression of PER protein was upregulated by CDDP treatment in CA9-22, but not in HGF-1 cells and PER1 knockdown

enhanced the apoptosis induced by CDDP treatment, and altered the protein expression of apoptosis-related factors, including Bim [28]. Our results were also accordant with the above reports.

Clock and brain-muscle-arnt-like-protein 1 (Bmal1) are dominant positive regulators of circadian rhythm. Many reports suggested that clock genes contribute to the regulation of not only circadian rhythm, but also the regulation of apoptosis induced by anti-tumour drugs. [30-31] data analysis of 14 different cancer types revealed that most of the core clock genes are differentially expressed between tumors and normal tissue counterparts. The analysis shown a trend of up- or downregulation that partially reflected the role of the corresponding clock protein in transcriptional activation or repression [31,32]. In our study the Bmal and Clock were found down regulated before treatment.

The transcriptional repressors PER1/2/3 and CRY1/2 are generally downregulated in tumors. Nevertheless, there are exceptions: a cancer-type-specific expression pattern was reported for several genes, including BMAL1 and NPAS2, which are upregulated in several tumors but downregulated in others [32]. It was also found that the tumor tissue of CRC patients, compared to their adjacent normal mucosa, BMAL1, PER1/2/3, and CRY2 were downregulated, whereas TIM was upregulated, and CLOCK and CRY1 revealed no changes in expression [33]. In metastatic melanomas, the expression of BMAL1, PER1/2/3, CRY1/2 and RORa was decreased, whereas CLOCK expression was increased. [34]. A study also found that the CLOCK and PER2 were downregulated, whereas BMAL1 was upregulated [31] in prostate cancer (PCa) in comparison to benign tissues. Overall, a number of studies, focusing mostly on single core

clock genes in a specific tumor type, reported recurring alteration in the expression level of clock genes in different tumors, as well as tumor-type-specific differences.

The expression of nine circadian clock genes PER1, PER2, PER3, CRY1, CRY2, CK1 ϵ , TIM, CLOCK and BMAL1 in tumor and non-tumor, adjacent tissue from 40 patients diagnosed with HNSCC has been reported [38]. Findings of studies shown that the expression level of PER genes, CRY1 and BMAL1 genes were significantly lower in HNSCC [30]. Of the seven-downregulated genes studied, the CRY2 was the most downregulated gene, a nine times decrease in tumor tissue compared to the non-tumor tissue was measured. Furthermore, it has also been established that downregulated PER3, CRY2 and BMAL1 was attributed to the more advanced stages of cancer. Moreover, analysis of 40 HNSCC patients' pathological reports, were done to examine the correlation of the circadian clock genes expression with HNSCC tumor-dependent variations. In the process, the patients were divided into two groups: one group with tumor size 3 cm and tumor depth >1 cm. Analysis indicated that amongst nine studied clock genes, transcripts of PER3 highlighted a tumor size-dependent variation and an invasive depth-dependent variable pattern. On the other hand, TIM displayed only a tumor size-dependent variation pattern. Furthermore, a bigger size of tumor was related with diminished PER3 and enhanced TIM expression, and increased tumor invasion was associated with decreased PER3 expression [5]. Analysis of the association between survival rates of the patients with altered circadian clock gene expression have been done with a follow-up of 2 years post-surgery. Prospective analysis was done assess any link between patient's survival status and circadian clock gene expression. It has been found that downregulation of PER1 and PER3 were correlated with poor survival rates [5]. In the same study, altered circadian clock gene expression was analyzed in the context of age differences and the patients were further stratified into young (30–45 years old), middle-age (45–60 years old) and old-age (60–80 years old) groups. It was found that the CK1 ϵ was significantly downregulated in the middle-age patient group in comparison with the young patient group. Expression of TIM was also significantly impaired in the middle-aged patient group in comparison with young and old-age groups. The authors assumed that in HNSCC, downregulated and disrupted circadian clock genes probably lost their function in removing pre-malignant and malignant cells leading to appearance of malignancies [28]. In addition, it was probable that deregulation of circadian machinery influences the molecules involved in cell cycle progression and apoptosis regulation, thus leading to cancer progression.

Hence, it has been hypothesized that circadian clock genes can regulate or suppress other circadian genes by certain mechanisms, which may also corroborate the finding on simultaneous lower expression levels of circadian gene such as PER1, PER2, PER3, CRY1, CRY2 and BMAL1 in HNSCC (Table 2) [30]. further reported on relationship between the circadian clock gene expression and severity of disease, tumor size, tumor invasion, survival rate. They found that various altered genes were associated with different clinical parameters. PER3 was the only gene correlated with all investigated parameters, though more profound investigations are required to elucidate the causes of PER3 deregulation in HNSCC in particular [29]. The authors also investigated alterations of nine clock genes, namely PER1, PER2, PER3, CRY1, CRY2, CLOCK, CK1 ϵ , BMAL1 and TIM in peripheral blood of HNSCC patients [27]. They found that all nine clock genes were downregulated and suggested the PER1 and CLOCK genes as potential circulating prognostic markers for HNSCC. Interestingly, CLOCK gene was the most downregulated gene among studied, nine-downregulated clock genes with at least a three times decrease in patients in comparison with healthy individuals. Tumor samples from both oral and non-oral areas were included in this study. It was again observed that the same CLOCK gene was the most downregulated one. It should be highlighted that the degree of CLOCK gene expression was significantly different between oral and non-oral tumors. Importantly, the recovery of PER1 and CLOCK expression in postoperative patients was correlated with good prognosis, the study hypothesized that downregulation of CLOCK gene inhibited protective function of NF- κ B activation [27,34]. Collectively, these data provide a good basis for pursuing investigations on the involvement of the highly complex circadian system and its core clock components in the malignant progression of HNSCC and other tumors as well. Our study was also in accordant with the above studies.

Only a few studies have studied the association between circadian genes and cisplatin. A study verifying the link between the CLOCK gene and cisplatin resistance treated cisplatin-resistant and cisplatin-sensitive ovarian cancer cells with varying concentrations of cisplatin. CLOCK protein expression amplified as cisplatin concentration increased in the cisplatin-resistant and cisplatin-sensitive cell lines in a dose-dependent way, suggesting that the CLOCK gene and protein were linked with cisplatin resistance in ovarian cancer cells causing an increase in cancerogenesis [33,35]. Our study was also accordant with the above study, Clock genes were (Bmal-1, Per-1-3, Cry-2) upregulated in Arm-I (Cisplatin +5 FU) as

compared to Arm-II (Cisplatin + Capecitabin), our results suggested that the treatment response was more in Arm-I group. In order to comprehend how the BMAL1 gene affects tumor growth and its response to cisplatin, a study examined the effect of knockdown of BMAL1 by RNAi. Downregulation of BMAL1 gene expression enhanced cell growth in vitro and promoted tumor growth in mice. Inhibiting BMAL1 expression in the mice's fibroblast cells and colon cancer cells decreased DNA damage caused by cisplatin. Knockdown of BMAL1 decreased the expression of PER1, PER2, PER3, and p53. BMAL1 contributes to regulating cell-cycle progression, tumor cell apoptosis, and DNA-damage response and in homeostasis regulation by accelerating the development of tumors and influencing the response to cisplatin [29]. These outcomes demonstrated that the interference of clock genes (CLOCK and BMAL1) can have opposite oncogenic effects. Our results were also agreeable with the above reports. c-myc stimulates either apoptosis or cell-cycle progression; c-myc expression levels closely relate to cell proliferation [20]. The expression of weel and PERs is controlled by the circadian variation of the complex CLOCK-BMAL1. PER genes act as

tumor suppressors. Overexpression of PER1 made human cancer cells susceptible to DNA damage-induced apoptosis; conversely, inhibition of PER1 in the same cells decreased cell death [21]. Cisplatin-focused chronotherapy has an advantage in alleviating side effects of anti-cancer drugs, and cisplatin can influence the circadian clock [22]. Past results present exciting outlooks for chemotherapy, in addition to other treatments that focus on DNA damage such as radiation therapy. However, the Chrono therapeutic use of cisplatin is in a delicate balance between augmenting the treatment of cancer and reducing unintended side effects. It is critical to recognize the mechanisms that affect Chrono therapeutic outcomes to find this right balance. Cisplatin can modulate the circadian clock causing an increase in cell proliferation [33]. It is worth noting that the effect of anti-cancer drugs on specific circadian genes is a novel area of exploration in chronotherapy research and more experimental data is necessary for a more definitive conclusion. Nonetheless, the considerable value that cisplatin offers patients with advanced cancer offsets the comparatively smaller risk of cell proliferation and cancerogenesis.

Figure 5: Drug discovery today-the circadian clock and cancer [30].

Conclusion

Circadian-clock genes form a unique system in living subjects. Further research focusing on these genes may, from the perspective of biological rhythms, provide novel ideas and methods for a better understanding of the occurrence and development of tumors, and for individualized treatment of cancer. Anti-cancer drugs like cisplatin affect components of the circadian clock causing either an increase or decrease in apoptosis and cell proliferation. When these drugs are

combined with each other or with other types of agents, they can have powerful anti-cancer effects. However, more work needs to be done before a conclusion can be drawn. More investigation of the underlying mechanisms behind chronotherapy, the effects of such responses to human physiology, the effect of tumorigenesis on the circadian cycles and the ability of the circadian clock to respond to chemotherapy are needed and would contribute greatly to advance anti-cancer chronotherapy. The results of this study suggest that the Clock genes

may be used as a marker to determine clinical staging, to evaluate the metastatic risk of OSCC, and as a novel target for the prevention and treatment of OSCC.

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